

Navigating the Analogue-Digital Divide and evolving Operational Structure of Lagos Television

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Abstract

This study explored the profound transformation that digitalisation has brought to Lagos Television (LTV), one of Nigeria's pioneering state-owned broadcasters, against the background of the country's protracted transition from analogue to digital broadcasting. Drawing on Marshall McLuhan's Media Ecology Theory, the research interrogates how shifts in media technology reshape institutional culture, operational structures and the relationship between broadcasters and their audiences. Using a qualitative approach with key informant interviews, the study engaged staff across engineering, news and new media departments spanning both analogue-era veterans and digital-era practitioners, to trace the evolution of LTV's workflows, production practices and organisational ethos. The findings reveal a departure from labour-intensive, tape-based and linear analogue systems towards a digitally driven environment characterised by automation, non-linear edition, real-time information flows and multi-platform distribution. Digitalisation has expanded LTV's reach through satellite and online streaming, enhanced production quality and enabled more dynamic audience engagement in an increasingly competitive media landscape. Yet the transformation remains uneven constrained by infrastructural deficits, funding limitations and the need for continuous staff retraining. The study concluded that while digitalisation has opened new horizons for LTV's relevance and survival, its full potential depends on sustained institutional commitment, technological investment and strategic adaptation to Nigeria's rapidly evolving media environment. The study recommended urgent government intervention by way of funding, infrastructure upgrade and staff training.

Keywords: Broadcasting, Digitalisation, Analogue, Media Ecology and Lagos Television

Introduction

Television broadcasting has long been a central pillar of mass communication, shaping public enlightenment, cultural identity, and entertainment. In Nigeria, the broadcast sector has undergone significant transformations, evolving from analogue to digital systems amidst complex institutional, infrastructural, and policy challenges. The

liberalisation of private television stations introduced competition and diversified ownership structures, yet analogue broadcasting remained limited in reach and quality.

Ogah (2020) observes that prior to digitisation, Nigeria operated 155 analogue stations, most of which were regional, with audiences restricted to a handful of channels. Similarly, Mediaaator UK (2014) reported that apart from the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA), no truly national network existed, leaving 70% of the population with access to four or fewer channels. Idachaba (2018, cited in Ogah 2020) further noted that analogue content was weak and inadequate, underscoring the urgency of reform.

Globally, the transition to Digital Terrestrial Television (DTT) has been driven by the promise of improved signal quality, efficiency, versatility, and interoperability with other electronic media. Digital broadcasting enables the seamless transmission of audio, video, and data, offering resistance to interference and facilitating multi-platform distribution. The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) set June 17, 2015, as the global deadline for analogue switch-off, mandating countries to migrate to digital systems (ITU, 2015). The ITU agreement granted several African countries, including Nigeria, a further five years until 2020 for the switchover completion (Oyedokun, Molindo & Ajayi, 2022). While many nations met this target, including six African nations (ITU, 2015), Nigeria's switchover has been slow and uneven, plagued by a lack of enthusiasm by the government, inadequate funding, and infrastructural deficits (Oladeji & Metin, 2022).

Against this backdrop, Lagos Television (LTV), one of Nigeria's pioneering state-owned broadcasters, provides a strong case study of the analogue-to-digital transition. Established in 1980 under the administration of Alhaji Lateef Jakande, LTV was the first state-owned station to operate on both VHF and UHF frequencies and later became the first to secure satellite presence. Its history reflects both resilience and vulnerability, from the devastating fire of 1985 to its eventual digital migration in 2008 under Governor Babatunde Raji Fashola. Today, LTV's journey exemplifies the broader national struggle to align with global broadcasting trends while contending with local institutional realities.

This study, therefore, interrogates how digitalisation has reshaped LTV's operational structures, production practices, and audience relationships. By situating LTV within Nigeria's protracted digital switchover and the global broadcasting environment, the research seeks to highlight both the opportunities and constraints of digitalisation in an ever-changing media ecology.

Statement of the Problem

The transition from analogue to digital broadcasting represents a fundamental restructuring of media production and distribution systems all over the world. In Nigeria, however, this transition has been uneven, protracted, and marked by significant institutional and infrastructural constraints. Lagos Television (LTV), as one of the country's foremost state-owned broadcasters, exemplifies the complexities inherent in navigating this analogue-digital divide. This study seeks to understand how the station adapts its operational structures in response to digitalisation and its influence on the overall operational environment.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the operational structure in the analogue and digital eras.
2. Discuss the influence of digitalisation on media operations in Lagos Television.

History of Lagos Television

Lagos Television was established in October 1980 under the administration of Alhaji Lateef Jakande to disseminate information and entertain the populace. It became the second television station to be founded by a state government, only preceded by the Broadcast Corporation of Oyo State (BCOS). It began broadcasting on November 9, 1980, and was the first station to operate on two frequencies/bands, UHF and VHF. Now on UHF Channel 35, it was the first state-owned television channel on satellite. The objective of LTV was to allow the state administration to disseminate information and entertain the general public, and to link the government and the populace.

In October 1980, the administration of Alhaji Lateef Jakande established its own television station to bolster its information dissemination machinery on November 9, 1980. LTV commenced transmission on Very High Frequency (VHF) channel 5. The formal review of the Nigerian communication law, as well as the return of military rule in 1983, engendered a new dawn in broadcasting, as there was a firm directive that all television stations apart from the NTA be restricted to the ultra-high frequency (UHF band). In compliance, Lagos television moved to UHF channel 35.

LTV was the first television station in Nigeria to operate on two frequencies - VHF and UHF simultaneously. This explains the station's former payoff - the power of television times 2. Apart from being the first television station from the NTA family, the station took the Nigerian television by storm in the 1980s with the introduction of a six-hour non-stop weekend transmission from 7 pm on Friday till 7 am on Monday. The then Lagos weekend television was the first marathon television station in Africa. Its unprecedented public approval transformed TV viewership, especially in the Lagos precinct, and brought a change to the call sign - LTV and LWT.

During those years, the operations of Lagos Television were not without their challenges. In September 1985, a mysterious midnight inferno consumed the entire legacy of the station. It destroyed the studios, library, offices, and equipment, even official records; personal effects of the staff were not spared.

For about one and a half years, LTV remained in the doldrums, merely surviving, but in 1995, Colonel Buba Marwa, the sole administrator of the state, set up a reorganisation committee to assess the position of the Lagos state broadcasting corporation and determine its need to survive. Subsequently, in 1998, under the administration of Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu, the recommendation of the committee was implemented, leading to the split of the LTV and the Radio services (formerly Lagos state broadcasting corporation) for better performance, autonomy, and career prospects for staff members. Within this period as well, the station received a fresh breath of life.

Following the universal shift from digital to analogue transmission, LTV became the first state-owned television on DSTV, and the formal switchover was performed by the Governor of Lagos, Mr. Babtunde Raji Fashola (SAN) in June 2008. The channel was later changed to 256. Subsequently, the station secured platforms on other satellites such as Startimes, GOTV, and PlayTV channel 950, increasing the station's visibility abroad. The live streaming facility (on TV and now Lagos Television apps) was another plus (Source: LTV website).

Switch to Digitalisation

Ezeaku (2024) explains that digitisation is a concept revolving around the media industry, including the print and electronic media. It is a process through which information, whether relayed through sound, text, voice, or image, is converted into digital binary language for computer use. The European Commission refers to the term 'switch-off' as the termination of terrestrial transmission of analogue television and "switchover" as the transition from analogue to digital broadcasting of all networks, including terrestrial, cable, satellite, and digital subscriber lines. The use of digital technology facilitates the coverage of computers, telecommunication, audio and visual, and consumer electrical and electronic gadgets. It is making a considerable impact on the broadcasting industry, on individuals, families, and on society as a whole. All governments attach great importance to digitisation and formulate policies and plans reflecting their active encouragement.

Globally, the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) met in Geneva, Switzerland, to deliberate and agree on a date for digitisation to take place. The group consisted of African, European, and Middle Eastern countries, and the timeframe for the switchover was June 2006, with a deadline of June 17, 2015. According to Oladeji & Metin (2022), just like other parts of the world, Nigeria was also mandated to switch over its broadcasting from analogue to digital. But contrary to global directives, Nigeria's switchover has been very slow due to a number of factors. The federal government, saddled with the responsibility of making the switch, has paid lip service to it. Just like other aspects of the country that have serious governmental neglect and institutional breakdown, this same snail-speed syndrome also plagues the switchover to digital broadcasting.

Ezeaku (2024) again notes that one major challenge with the analogue cable industry was the non-addressability of cable systems. Addressability can be achieved when the subscriber base is auditable and verifiable. The actual number of subscribers was unknown because the information was available only to the local cable operators, who often undervalued the amount collected, so the broadcasters had to incur heavy losses in revenue. Furthermore, analogue transmission does not support emerging technologies like High Definition (HD). It does not provide a good quality viewing experience to the end user and has limitations on the number of channels that can be carried on an analogue transmission (between 60 and 70), of which only 10-12 are of good quality, whereas a digital-based system can carry over 1,000 channels.

Digitisation requires a lot of financial commitment on the part of the government and its communication parastatals, as well as those in the private sector. To see this kind of venture through, the determination to see it work must be unaltered at any given time. By surmising, digitisation for the broadcasting media will upgrade sound and visual quality. For a very long time, the country has stuck to the traditional ways of broadcasting and transmission, which are very expensive and low in quality. Normally, you are required to have huge infrastructures put in place in order to broadcast and run a TV station or radio channel. But with the advent of digitisation and information technology, the whole process has been streamlined and is easy to carry out. For instance, the traditional ways of broadcasting involved Morse code transmission, while the new broadcasting can be carried out via the internet.

Advent of the Internet and Significant Shifts in Traditional Media Operations

In recent years, rapidly developing technology has been fuelling an information revolution. The new media which enables digital broadcasting is sweeping away the limitations of the analogue world and weakening the grip of government-owned platforms. Agboola (2014) explains that the nature of the relationship between the broadcaster and its audience is changing. New media in this information age provide an immediate, informative, intelligent, and interactive platform for discussing and debating. New media is essentially a cyber-culture with modern computer technology, digital data controlled by software, and the latest fast-developing communication technology. Most technologies described as new media are digital and often have characteristics of being networkable, dense, compressible, interactive, and impartial. Examples are the internet, websites, and computer multimedia. Today, people are attracted to the easy means of getting information with internet-based terminals or hand phones, which provide them with information of their choice anytime, anywhere. They do not need to wait for any broadcasting schedule to be connected to get the information. It therefore behoves broadcast stations to move at the speed of the internet or become a byword in the media business.

Empirical Studies

Oyedokun, Molindo & Ajayi (2022) carried out a study titled: ‘Analogue to Digital Switchover; an inquiry into the progress, challenges, and benefits of digitising the Nigerian broadcast sector.’ The study employed a library research technique and utilised technological determinism theory. According to the findings, digital television produces crispier pictures and sounds, the signals are less prone to distortion and the audience will be provided with numerous channels to choose from. They noted, at the time, that the digitisation process had been completed in Plateau state, Abuja, Kwara, Osun, Enugu, Kaduna and Lagos, yet the process had faced some challenges, such as inadequate funding, scarcity of qualified manpower, inadequate power supply, citizens' unawareness, and inadequate digital equipment. They conclude that until these and other relevant issues are resolved, a successful migration from analogue to digital broadcasting may be

unachievable in time in Nigeria. They recommend that the government should provide enough financial resources to fund the switchover, and the concerned agencies should embark on rigorous publicity because there are still many Nigerians who are unaware of the initiative.

Benike (2022) studied Migration from Analogue to Digital Broadcasting: The Disparity between Government and Private Media Stations in Delta State. The objective of the study was to examine the availability of digital equipment, the patterns of equipment use and the impact of digital broadcast equipment in government and private media stations. Anchored on the technological determinism theory, and using a cross-sectional research design on a sample of 186 media staff, the study revealed that digital equipment is available in both government and private media stations (82.2% in government and 70% in private) but is employed more by private media outfits. This marked disparity gives private stations greater impact. The study recommends that the government should encourage the training of media personnel to enable them to handle digital equipment to ensure better services to consumers.

Oladeji & Metin (2022), in an article titled “digitisation of Broadcasting in Nigeria: The journey so far and the way forward,” set out to examine the steps taken so far in Nigeria’s switchover, the prevailing challenges and the potential benefits for government, broadcasters, and viewers. Using a descriptive methodology that drew on secondary sources, government reports, and comparative case studies such as Slovenia’s experience, the research highlighted the gap between Nigeria’s aspirations and its actual progress. The findings revealed that repeated government postponements, lack of political will, inadequate funding, weak institutional frameworks, and legal disputes have significantly delayed the process. Furthermore, technical and financial challenges, including the high cost of equipment, insufficient skilled manpower, and poor public awareness, further compound the problem. The study recommended stronger government commitment, adequate funding for infrastructure and training, clear regulatory frameworks to avoid disputes, and intensified public sensitisation campaigns. It also emphasises that collaboration between the government, private broadcasters, and international partners is crucial to accelerate the transition. Ultimately, while digitisation offers immense benefits, its realisation in Nigeria depends on overcoming entrenched systemic barriers through decisive leadership and coordinated stakeholder action.

Theoretical Framework

This study employed media ecology theory to explain the study. Media ecology is a field of study that examines the complex relationship between media, technology, and society. It explores how different forms of media, from the printing press to the internet, shape our perception, behaviour and culture. The term was first coined by communication scholar Marshall McLuhan in the 1960s, who believed that different media technologies were like environments that shape the way people think, feel, and interact with one another. He was famous for saying that *the medium is the message*, meaning that the form of the medium has a greater impact on the human psyche than the content it carries.

Media ecology seeks to understand the impact of media on society by analysing how different media shape human perception, communication, and culture. It explores how media affect individual and collective consciousness and how they shape social structures and relationships. It is an interdisciplinary field that draws on a range of disciplines, including communication studies, sociology, anthropology, psychology and philosophy. It provides a framework for understanding the social, cultural, and psychological implications of media and technology and encourages critical thinking about the role of media in shaping our world. Khalid, Riaz & Farooq (2025) explain that Media ecology seeks to understand the impact of media on society by analysing how different media affect individual and collective consciousness and how they shape social structures and relationships.

Relating this theory to the study means appraising how LTV's operational structures adapt to the changing media landscape. The analogue media structure had a top-down approach with clear lines of authority, as noted in the organogram of the station, traditional workspaces - using obsolete equipment and limited engagement with the audience. Fast forward to the digital era, and there is more collaboration, a premium placed on digital content and distribution enhanced by the internet and an audience-focused approach to broadcasting. Therefore, to remain relevant as a key player in the broadcast industry, LTV must pay attention to the media ecology in Nigeria and align itself with global standards.

Methodology

A qualitative assessment was conducted at Lagos Television over three weeks between August and September 2025. The aim was to examine the operational structures in the analogue and digital transmission eras with an emphasis on the influence of digitalisation on media operations in Lagos Television.

The study captures learning directly from staff across management levels and with different years of experience (from both analogue and digital eras, 2 from the 1980s, and 2 from the 2000s) in Lagos Television. The qualitative assessment included a desk review of LTV's website and key informant interviews with staff.

The sample size included staff from the engineering department because of their centrality to the transition. The total population of the department involved was twenty-five but only four were interviewed due to the nature of the organisation. Key informants were purposively sampled with a focus on the technical teams directly involved with migrating from analogue to digital transmission. The findings discussed are drawn from data collected from various sources. Before commencing data collection, all participants provided oral informed consent. Careful note-taking and voice recording were made, including capturing non-verbal reactions. The data were analysed using Malterud's systematic text condensation, an explorative and descriptive thematic analysis method (Malterud, 2012).

Results

The study included four participants, and two thematic areas appeared from the analysis, including Operational Structures in the Analogue versus Digital Era and the Influence of Digitisation on the Media Operations in LTV

Operational Structures in the Analogue versus Digital Era

During the analogue era in LTV, the studio was equipped with analogue video cameras, boom microphones, lighting rigs, and physical sets. A vision mixer was used to switch between camera feeds during live or recorded productions. The sound was accessed by analogue mixers, which controlled sound levels from microphones and teleprompters operated manually or mechanically for news and scripted programmes. Today, the entire station wears a new look with high-technology equipment.

Participant 1 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) explains that:

“Essentially, a multi-purpose studio was put in place. Recruitment of creative personnel- the Technicians, Engineers, Producers, Graphic and Design staff, Librarian, Carpenters, Cameramen, Presentation staff, TV Journalists, make-up staff, and Photographers. A Hall that housed the transmitter was built, the transmitting mast, Video Camera Recorder (VCR), Electronic News Gathering (ENG), Cameras, Recorders aka 2630, microphones, Video tapes, construction of sets and flats. Most of these human and material resources were not readily available and could not be readily purchased from the shelf.”

Participant 2 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) corroborates this:

“From the 80s and 90s, the common tape then was VHS, and later on, we moved majorly to mini-DVD in the 2000s; it was very small, portable, about the size of a pack of four AA batteries, and cameras were using it. We had tape decks that were used for playbacks and recording. Those were available since way back. Studio cameras were mostly HD at the time, even though the resolution is higher now. We have 1080 now.”

Speaking about the structure of the station, participant 4 (personal communication, 15th September, 2025) observed that:

“Lagos Television (LTV), at its birth on November 9th, 1980, was established by the first Executive Governor of Lagos State, Alhaji Lateef Kayode Jakande, and under the Lagos State Broadcasting Corporation (LSBC). It had a crop of remarkably dedicated staff - all with a sense of mission.

There was the Engineering Department, headed by Engr. Ilésanní Idowu. In the News Department, Alhaji T. A. Musa, a seasoned

television journalist, was the Head. He was supported by a blend of old and fresh minds in television journalism. In the Programme Department were the talented and creative men and women, like Jimi Odumosu, who became the GM of the Station. The Graphics and Designs was headed by the late Mrs. Olayinka Ojeyinka, supported by talented staff.

LTV television broadcasting belonged to the analogue system of transmitting signals. It had committed staff, dedicated leadership, and good programming that constituted the main ingredients for the success of the station. A point of reference, I hold, is the trick adopted by LTV. At its take-off, the station was the darling of Lagosians; its programming was a master key that scared NTA 10, it competed strongly with NTA Ibadan, and the NTA Ikeja found it hard to beat.

The most crucial aspect of a successful analogue television is the running of its schedule to make a difference and affect the viewing audience.”

Referring to the pattern of editing in the analogue era, Participant 3 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) mentions that:

“After capturing news and events, editors utilised linear editing systems with VCR decks to cut and assemble footage, also, graphics generation was employed for basic character generators, titles, and captions. For sound editing, sound managers used reel-to-reel cassette systems for voice-overs and background music. The station also had a tape library for storing VHS, U-matic, or Betacam tapes containing programmes, adverts, and archival footage. For record keeping of tape contents, durations, and air dates, handwritten log sheets were provided, and staff manually scheduled daily programming, often displaying them on whiteboards or printed paper.”

Participant 2 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) explains that:

“In the days of VHS tapes, recorded material had to be captured onto a PC using a capture card, edited, and then transferred to a VHS tape. At the Master Control Room, the final output is sent to the transmitter using analogue signal processors and modulators. LTV was broadcasting both in very high frequency and ultra-high frequency simultaneously from 1980 to 1983.”

Contrasting analogue and digital operations, participant 2 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) mentioned that:

“There is new equipment which is different from what we had. We can't compare them, there's transition and there's technological

improvement, we have newer cameras, the station was set up in the analogue days, even the building was different. What we have today is different from what we had before. There were no computers or the internet in those days. Now, we can even get information on our phones. In those days, we had to be on the ground for events, but now, you may decide not to even go and use the internet.”

Participant 3 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) mirrored the same sentiment:

“With the advent of technology, most analogue devices are getting older and outdated. You can’t even find a brand new one of them to buy (analogue devices). Most manufacturers have phased them out. We are moving out a lot of devices. We no longer use tapes (miniDV) and have a lot of digital facilities; we are now moving to memory cards, which we store basically as data. We are not playing; we simply copy and paste. Most of the processing equipment requires digital technology, converting from one format to another, sending files over a network, which is the basic operation.”

Explaining the workings at the news desk, participant 4 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) explained that:

“Journalists were appointed to beats, and most times for events, an invitation card would be brought to the studio. Stories were also written on typewriters. Reporters used analogue cameras and physically turned in tape recordings.”

Comparing the analogue and digital era, participant 2 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) explains that:

“Even till now, that is still a work in progress because there is no full conversion anywhere for a TV station except those that started as digital. They are the ones that have been digital from the beginning. Everybody else still does analogue transmission (terrestrial), sending to a transmitter, and then sending out. But everybody knows digital transmission as well, sending to a digital satellite TV station. They all have their ways of receiving the signal, and then they take care of the transmission. Even though the government has said everyone should move, it hasn’t been final. It doesn’t look as if it is going to be a final stage because most people are still doing both together - using transmitters and using digital means - either you are sending to a digital satellite TV station or sending online.”

All participants noted that going digital was inevitable; it was both a national and global move, and no one could afford to be left out. Available frequencies were being changed globally, and even manufacturers were producing more digital equipment. Digitisation is a move to stay relevant and have access to a new audience.

Influence of Digitalisation on Media Operations in LTV

Digital broadcasting has far-reaching influence on every aspect of the media operations in a broadcast station and it provides enormous benefits to all stakeholders, including audiences and broadcasters. These advantages come in the form of programme contents, high-quality transmissions, media convergence, and many channels, and various sections of society gain from it. Oyedokun, Molindo & Ajayi (2022) mention that with digital transmission, broadcasters will enter a new age of cost-effectiveness. This is because a station can transmit up to four channels on the same frequency. Furthermore, digital programme development is more versatile and quicker than analogue, and stations may rely on syndicated programming in general since the digitisation process promotes equitable chances, resulting in good competition.

Participant 3 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) noted that:

“Digitisation sets you on a higher pedestal; there is more efficiency and productivity; workload is reduced because there is automation in production and editing, you are open to the world, you can get information in real time, and there are so many advantages. Digital signals improve signal quality and coverage, you have wider coverage and better transmission. Also there is faster delivery of content.”

One major influence and benefit that LTV enjoys in a highly competitive media market is access to digital space. Participant 2 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025) explains the benefit to the audience and the economic impact on the station:

“There is greater audience engagement, viewers gain access to interactive features such as electronic programme guides and subtitles. Digitisation supports integration with online platforms, expanding reach beyond terrestrial signals. But the high cost of the infrastructure upgrade in terms of digital transmitter, studio equipment and staff training are quite challenging for the station.”

Participant 3 corroborates this:

“For LTV, so far, one major influence is with audience engagement in the digital space beyond our terrestrial offer. Even when we have issues with the electricity supply, we have a digital audience and we are streaming live. We are sending to our digital satellite TV station, and people can watch, which helps. At least we have viewers in the digital space. With the way technology is, everyone has gone mobile. If you can't be seen on a mobile device, then you can't be seen by a certain

audience. If they can't see you on the phone, then you have lost the. Some still sit in front of their TV, but many are online, so that keeps us in touch with many of our audiences.”

Participant 4 (personal communication, 15th September, 2025) mentioned that: “Our social media is effective. We stream live on YouTube, and we also have an application. YouTube has censorship, and we don’t have enough materials of our own, but with the app, more people can be reached without censorship. Most TV stations are mobile, and terrestrial doesn’t reach everyone as such.”

Participant 1 (personal communication, 21st August, 2025), sharing this same sentiment, echoes that:

“For regular transmission - terrestrial or analogue, the same signal is going out on all the platforms, but we now have a team that focuses on social media, streaming devices, and web outputs. We have that. But for analogue TV, terrestrial viewers and those who receive digital satellite are coming from the same output, so just make sure. It is only social media that has different content. We have someone who heads the social media unit. That office is directly under the General Manager.”

Discussion of Findings

This study has provided detailed insights into the ways that LTV is gradually progressing from analogue to digital operations, with important implications for the advancement of the station. The qualitative interview approach has provided rich data that offer a multifaceted understanding of how LTV has evolved in the analogue era and now in the digital era. Based on a sample of four officials in one station, this study provides a generalisable or representative picture of the analogue-digital transition issue in Lagos Television, and the presence of certain themes described by participants suggests that these might be widely held, which could be confirmed by further research. The interviews revealed themes with relevance to analogue-digital switch over, which are discussed.

The findings from this qualitative assessment with officials of the Lagos Television highlight the need to reconsider the prospects of digitisation and align with the inherent benefits. It is noted that there has been a significant shift from analogue to digital transmission, as witnessed by the improvements in some infrastructure, as well as the leverage provided by the internet and social media platforms. While it is commendable to note that LTV has found a way to improvise and hang on to analogue while dancing on the digital platform, there is a need to fully harness the benefits of digitisation and align with current trends in the world, and this is desperately dependent on funding, manpower training, and infrastructure upgrade. This mirrors the findings of Oyedokun, Molindo &

Ajayi (2022) and Oladeji & Metin (2022), who emphasise that inadequate funding, scarcity of qualified manpower, inadequate power supply, citizens' unawareness, and inadequate digital equipment are hindrances to a successful migration from analogue to digital broadcasting. It also aligns with the findings of Benike (2022), who insists that manpower training can bring about a marked shift in the movement from analogue to digital television broadcasting, especially in government-owned media stations. This further corroborates the media ecology theory, considering that LTV is navigating the shift from analogue to digital, a transformation that is not merely technical but deeply ecological in media terms. It is not just a hardware upgrade, but a paradigm shift in how information is produced, distributed, and consumed. Digital media introduces new features - interactivity, speed, and decentralisation that reshape institutional workflows, audience expectations, and content formats. Furthermore, LTV's improvisation with analogue and digital reflects media hybridity, a transitional ecosystem where old and new media coexist.

Additionally, the rise of the internet and social media platforms introduces new centres of influence at LTV, challenging the traditional broadcast structures. This reflects the aspect of media ecology that explains the reconfiguration of media power, where control over narrative and audience engagement shifts from centralised institutions to more fluid networked environments.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study has highlighted the complex dynamics surrounding Lagos Television's gradual shift from analogue to digital broadcasting. Using key informant interviews, it was evident from the study that while there are signs of progress, such as infrastructural upgrades and the integration of internet-based platforms, the station continues to struggle under the weight of a hybrid system, reflecting a fluctuating media ecology. The shift is more than a technical upgrade; it is a transformation of the communication environment that redefines institutional roles, audience relationships, and operational norms. The stations' improvisational strategies show resilience but also underscore the urgent need for strategic support to fully harness the benefits of digital media. The following recommendations are thereby proposed:

1. The Lagos state government should prioritise digitisation as a public necessity and an essential civic infrastructure (not just a commercial entity) and allocate dedicated financial resources to support infrastructure, training, and content creation.
2. LTV needs to invest in continuous professional development for staff, especially key staff involved in the technical aspects team, to manage the equipment effectively.
3. As a matter of urgency, attention should be focused on upgrading transmission equipment and improving power supply systems to support full digital operations.

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